

EVALUATION OF EFFICACY OF TRIPHALA CHURNA WITH MURCHHITA GHRITA IN PANDU ROGA– A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON SAMANYA VISHESH SIDDHANT

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INTRODUCTION

Maintaining optimal health and mitigating disease by using Ayurvedic medicine is the goal of Ayurveda. Ayurveda emphasizes the balance between body, mind and soul for healthy living.

त्रिफला सर्वरोगघ्नी त्रिभागघृतमुर्च्छिता I^[1]

In *Sutrasthana* of *Sushruta Samhita Virechana-Dravya-Vikalpa Vigyaniya-Adhyaya* above *Siddhant* is given. This research is done only for applicability of *Siddhant* in today's era in particular one disease called *Pandu-Roga*, due to lack of time and numerous number of disease. Considering a Prevalence of *Pandu* in the society, a thought to treat the *Pandu* by *Samanya Vishesh Siddhant*. *Triphala Churna* with *Ghrita* has yet not been studied on *Pandu Roga*, these formulation is said to be *Sarvarogaghani* by Sushruta.^[1] Keeping all these views in

mind and cost effective therapy, great hopes are being laid on the ayurvedic science, which will help to prevent the complication and hazardous effects and act as an adjuvant therapy in *Pandu Roga*. The main aim is being able to provide guideline for maintenance and getting health as well as prevention and treatment of diseases. In other words, Ayurveda is a science which helps in understanding aspect of life, happy and unhappy life, congenial and non-congenial for life, life span, and also corporal dimensions.

The present study is an attempt to analyze the efficacy of *Triphala Churna* with *Murchhita Ghrita* in the management of *Pandu Roga*. The study has been performed as under with comparison between same group of patients as before treatment and after treatment. So, to find whether *Triphala Churna* with *Murchhita Ghrita* shows any change in haemogram level in *Pandu Roga* with the help of *Samanya Vishesh Siddhant*. So, the study is carried out to find out the unbiased result.

AIM

1. To evaluate the efficacy of *Triphala Churna* with *Murchhita Ghrita* in *Pandu Roga* with special reference to *Samanya Vishesh Siddhant*.

OBJECTIVES

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

1. To study the efficacy of *Triphala Churna* and *Murchhita Ghrita* on sign and symptoms of *Pandu Roga* and Hb% with special reference to *Samanya Vishesh Siddhant*.
2. To assess the *Guna's* of sign and symptoms of *Pandu Roga* and to study *Samanya Vishesh Siddhant*.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

- 1) To study *Guna's* of *Triphala Churna* with *Murchhita Ghrita*.
- 2) To assess the *Guna's* of *Pandu Roga* with sign and symptoms.
- 3) To study the *Samanya Vishesh Siddhant*.

Review of Literature

Nidan-Panchaka: - [Diagnostic tools of Ayurveda]

Nidan, *Poorva-Roopa*, *Roopa*, *Upashaya* & *Samprapti* are the five diagnostic stool used for the diagnosis of diseases and treating it.^[25]

Aharaja Hetu

Sr. No.	Factors	CHA	SU	VAG	M.N.	HA	BHAV
1	<i>Tikshna Ahar-Atisevana</i>	-	+	+	+	-	+
2	<i>Ushna Aharatisevana</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
3	<i>Lavana rasa Atisevana</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+
4	<i>Kashay Rasa Atisevana</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
5	<i>Ksharasevan</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
6	<i>Abhojana</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
7	<i>Pramitabhोजना</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-

8	<i>Mridbhakshana</i>	+	+	-	+	+	+
9	<i>Masha Sevana</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
10	<i>Pinyakasevana</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
11	<i>Til Tail Sevana</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
12	<i>Asatmyasevana</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
13	<i>Virudhabhojana</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
14	<i>Madhya Sevan</i>	-	+	-	+	+	+

Viharaja Hetu

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Factor</i>	<i>CHA</i>	<i>SU</i>	<i>VAG</i>	<i>M.N.</i>	<i>HA</i>	<i>BHAV</i>
1	<i>Ratrijagaran</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
2	<i>Vegaavrodh</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
3	<i>Ativyavay</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
4	<i>Ativyayam</i>	+	+	-	+	-	+
5	<i>Rituvaiashmya</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	<i>Diwasapna</i>	+	+	-	+	-	+
7	<i>Atiadhvagaman</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
8	<i>Sharirikadhikshrama</i>	-	-	+	-	-	-

Manas Hetu

<i>Sr. No</i>	<i>FACTORS</i>	<i>CHA</i>	<i>SU</i>	<i>VAG</i>	<i>M.N</i>	<i>HA</i>	<i>BHAV</i>
1	<i>KAMA</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
2	<i>KRODHA</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
3	<i>SHOKA</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
4	<i>CHINTA</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
5	<i>BHAYA</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-

Purvaropa of Panduroga

<i>Puravaropa</i>	<i>Cha</i>	<i>Su</i>	<i>A. H</i>	<i>M.N</i>	<i>Ha</i>
<i>Akshikutshoth</i>	-	+	-	+	-
<i>Avipaka</i>	-	+	-	+	-
<i>Aruchi</i>	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Agnimandya</i>	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Angsada</i>	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Gatrasada</i>	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Hritspandanam</i>	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Mutrapiyata</i>	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Mridbhakshaneshchha</i>	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Rukshata</i>	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Swedabhava</i>	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Sthivanadhikya</i>	-	+	-	+	-
<i>Shrama</i>	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Twaksphutana</i>	-	+	-	+	+
<i>Varchapitatvam</i>	-	+	+	+	+

Lakshana's of Pandu Roga**Vattaja Pandu Lakshana's**

Roopa	Cha	Su	A H(Ni 11/09)	M.N. P.	Ha	Bhav
<i>Arunanakhatva</i>	-	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Arunasiratva</i>	-	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Arunanetrata</i>	-	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Angamarda</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Angaruka</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Angaatopa</i>	+	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Asyavairasya</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Anaha</i>	+	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Arunvitaka</i>	-	-	+	-	-	+
<i>Balakshaya</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Brama</i>	-	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Darunakoshtha</i>	-	-	-	-	+	+
<i>Gandharvitakta</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Krishnanetratva</i>	-	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Krishnapanduta</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Krishnasira</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Krishnanakhatva</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Krishnaanantatva</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Netrapitatva</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Nakhapitatva</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Mutrapiyata -</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Parushtva</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Parshvaruka</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Rukshangata</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Rukshanetrata</i>	-	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Rukshasiratva -</i>	-	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Rukshamutrata</i>	-	-	+	+	+	-
<i>Ruksha Krishna Arunatvaka</i>	-	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Shioruka</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Shirogurava</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Shofa</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-

Pittaja Pandu Lakshana's

Sr. No	Laksahna	C. S	Su	A H (N 13/10)	MD	Bhav	Ha
1	<i>Annabhinandan</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
2	<i>Amlanupashayata</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
3	<i>Amatva</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+
4	<i>Atipitabha</i>	-	-	-	+	-	-
5	<i>Bhinnavarchasatva</i>	+	+	-	-	-	-
6	<i>Chhardi</i>	+	+	-	-	-	-
7	<i>Daugandhya</i>	+	+	+	-	-	+
8	<i>Daha</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-
9	<i>Haritabhata</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-

10	<i>Haritasiratva</i>	-	-	+	-	-	+
11	<i>Jwara</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+
12	<i>Katukasyata</i>	+	+	-	-	-	+
13	<i>Murcha</i>	+	+	+	-	-	+
14	<i>Pitata</i>	+	+	-	-	-	+
15	<i>Pitekshanatva</i>	-	+	+	+	-	-
16	<i>Pitanakhatva</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-
17	<i>Pitaanantva</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-
18	<i>Pitachhavi</i>	-	+	-	-	-	-
19	<i>Pitamutrata</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-
20	<i>Pitavitakta</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-
21	<i>Sweda</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-
22	<i>Shitakamita</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-

Kaphaja Pandu Lakshana's

Sr. No	Lakshana	C	Su	A H (Ni 13/11)	M.N	B	Ha
1	<i>Alasya</i>	+					+
2	<i>Aruchi</i>	+					
3	<i>Bhrama</i>	+					
4	<i>Chhardi</i>	+		+			
5	<i>Gaurava</i>	+			+		+
6	<i>Klama</i>	+					
7	<i>Kasa</i>	+		+			
8	<i>Lomaharsha</i>	+		+			
9	<i>Lavanavakratata</i>		+	+			
10	<i>Murcha</i>	+					
11	<i>Madhurasyata</i>	+					
12	<i>Praseka</i>	+			+		
13	<i>Rukshakamata</i>	+					
14	<i>Shvetavabhasata</i>	+					
15	<i>Shuklakshita</i>	+	+	+	+		
16	<i>Shuklaanantva</i>		+	+			
17	<i>Shuklanakhatva</i>		+	+	+		
18	<i>Shuklasiravanddhta</i>		+	+			
19	<i>Sada</i>	+					
20	<i>Shwasa</i>	+					
21	<i>Swaragraha</i>	+					
22	<i>Swarakshaya</i>			+			
23	<i>Shuklamutrata</i>	+	+		+		
24	<i>Shuklavarchasa</i>				+		
25	<i>Shuklatwaka</i>				+		
26	<i>Tandra</i>	+			+		+
27	<i>Ushnakamta</i>	+					

Sannipataja Pandu

Due to vitiation of all the three humors shows following symptoms,

- Fever,

- anorexia,
- nausea,
- vomiting,
- thirst and
- Fatigue.

Patient has weakness and patients should be discarded from the treatment as incurable.

Mritikabhakshanjanya Panduroga^[50, & 51]

A person who eats mud cakes, his all humors (*Doshas*) get vitiated according to the type of the earth, such as

- 1) *Vata* ----astringent tasting earth,
- 2) *Pitta*----- alkaline(salty) earth
- 3) *Kapha* -----sweet tasting earth

After having the mud, due to its *Ruksha Guna* the ingested meal which, in turn, remains undigested, occupies and blocks the *strotas*.The bodily luster, potency and ojas, thereby producing anemia (*Pandu Roga*) readily which destroys strength, colour and digestion of the patient. There is edema around the orbits, the cheeks and the eyebrows and also in the feet, at umbilical region and the penis. The patient develops intestinal worms and passes loose stools with blood and mucus.

Samprapti

Pandu-Roga Ghataka.

- 1) *Dosha – Tridosha [Samanya Vyadhi]*
- 2) *Dushya – Rasa, Rakta, Mansa mainly*
- 3) *Agni – Jathar Agnimandya & Dhatwa Agnimandya*
- 4) *Srotas – Rasavahastrotas*
- 5) *Srotodushti – Sanga*
- 6) *Udbhavasthana – Yakrita & Pleeha*
- 7) *Adhisthana – Sarva Sharira*
- 8) *Vyaktasthana – Twak*
- 9) *Rogamarga – Abhyantara & Kosthagata.*

TRIDOSHA**Pittaj Dosha**

Pitta Dosha and *Rakta Dhatu* has *Ashray-Ashrayi* relationship. When the *Pitta Dosha* gets vitiated indirectly because of almost same *Guna's Rakta Dhatu* to get imbalanced. So, following results are seen,

- *Sadhak Pitta*: - *Hridaya Daurbalya*, its *Mansik Hetu*.
- *Pachak Pitta*: - hampers *Prinan & Jivan Karma* of *Hetu*.
- *Ranjak Pitta*: -*Twak Vaivaran, Netra Pandutava* etc.
- *Bhrajak Pitta*: - its *Dushti* results in *Pandutava* of skin, eyes, urine, etc

Vattaj Dosha

Vyan Vayu is most important factor for the cause of *Pandu Roga* because it takes and spread the *Aam Yukta Ahara Ras* in whole body. The vitiated *Dosha's* gets *Sthana-Sanshraya* in between the skin and muscles. results in *Pandutava Lakshana's* of disease.

Kaphaj Dosha

Pitta dominant *Tri-dosha* are responsible for *Pandu-Roga*. It's a *Santarpanjanya Vyadhi* said by Charak.^[55]

Arishta in Pandu-Roga

Pandu-Rogi having swelling, yellowish eye, yellowish nails, and the skin colour turns into yellow.^[56]

CHIKITSA IN PANDU-ROGA^[57]

Yuktivyapashraya Chikitsa the type of *Chikitsa* used to treat *Pandu-Roga* Is more beneficial for patients. *Sanhodhan & sanshamana* is the main treatment for *Pandu Roga*.

It includes all the following title

- *Sanshaman Chikitsa*
- *Shodhan Chikitsa*
- *Vishista Chikitsa*
- *Pathya-Apathya Chikitsa*
- *Vanaspatic Yoga*
- *Khanija Yoga*

Sanshamana Chikitsa

It's a kind of treatment in which the imbalance *Dosha's* are brought to a normal level by *Ahar*, *Viahara* and *Aushadhi*. Mostly in *Pandu-Roga* treatment is *Pitta Dosha Prasadaka*, and *Tridosha shamaka*.

Single Drugs.

- *Haritaki*
- *Guduchi*
- *Bhumiamalki*
- *Vanshalochana*
- *Triphala*
- *Kokilaksha*
- *Tinisha*
- *Khadir*
- *Trivritta*
- *Katak*
- *Haridra*
- *Koshataki*
- *Punarnava*
- *Bimbi*

Shodhan Chikitsa

- *Shodhan* is the method of eliminating the vitiated *Doshas* from the body to pacify the disease.^[58]
- In *Panduroga Chikitsa*, *Shodhan Chikitsa* is very essential to break the root cause. In *Pandu Roga* patient should be given emetic (*Vamana*) and purgation (*Virechana*).^[59]
Vamanartha Yoga
- *Kothaphala*
- *Kritavedhan*
- *Ikshwaku*
Virechana Yoga^[60]
- Luck warm infusion of Danti, sprinkled with powder of *Kasmari* (fruit of Gambhari) or mixed with the paste of *Draksha*.

- *Haritaki* added with Cows urine.
- Milk alone

Churna

- *NavayasChurna*
- *HaritkyadiChurna*
- *GudaHaritakiChurna*
- *TrivrittaChurna*
- *VishaladiChurna*
- *SwarnkshiradiYoga*

Kwatha / Fant Kalpana

- *VishaladiFant*
- *DarvyadiKwath*
- *PunarnavadiKwath*
- *Triphala Kwath*

Vati

- *Mandurvatak*
- *Yogaraj*
- *Shilajatu Vatak*
- *Mandurvajravatak*
- *PunarnavaMandur*
- *Vajra Vatak*
- *Bibhitakadi Vataka*
- *Mandurlavana*
- *Madhumandura*
- *Shivagutika*
- *Nishaloha*
- *Dhatriloha*
- *Navayasloha*

Ghrita

- *DadimGhrita*

- *PathyaGhrita*
- *DrakshaGhrita*
- *katukadyaGhrita*
- *DantiGhrita*
- *HaritkyadiGrita*

Arishtha Kalpana

- *Dhatryarishtha*
- *Bijakarishtha*
- *Gaudarishtha*
- *Gandirarishtha*

Grihhta used for Snehana

- *MahatiktakGhrit*
- *PathyaGhrit*
- *DadimadiGhrit*
- *MurvadyaGhrit*
- *KalyanakGhrit*
- *DantiGhrit*
- *DrakshaGhrit*
- *BhruhatyadiGhrit*
- *AragvadhadihanaSidhhaGhrit*
- *HaridradiGhrit*
- *KatukarohinyadiGhrit*
- *PanchagavyaGhrit*

Gunatmaka Chikitsa Siddhanata^[61]

Table No-8.

<i>Doshaja Pandu</i>	<i>Treatment</i>
<i>Vattaj Pandu</i>	<i>Snigdha Gunatmaka Chikitsa</i>
<i>Pittaja Pandu</i>	<i>Tikta & Shita Gunatmaka Chikitsa</i>
<i>Kaphaja Pandu</i>	<i>Katu, Ruksha, & Ushana Gunatmaka Chikitsa</i>

Pathya-Apathya

- 1) Barley, Wheat, Sahi paddy, Rice, Jangal meat ras, Moong, lentil etc are *pathya*.^[62]

- 2) Fruits – *Draksha, Khajur, Amla* can be taken in *Pandu –Roga*
- 3) *Panchamula Siddha Jala* if *Vata Dosha* is prominent.
Musta, Hribera, Sunthi Siddha Jala if *Pitta dosha* is prominent.
- 4) *Arishta, Shidhu, Draksha, Asava* is given if *Kapha Dosha* is prominent. *Takra* is beneficial in every condition.^[63]
- 5) *Pandu-rogi* should give up the heat of fire, incense, exertion, bile stimulating food, sexual intercourse, anger, transit, etc, all this are apathy.

Dhatu

Utpattikrama of Dhatu

Ras, Rakta, Mansa, Meda, Asthi, Majja & Shukra are the seven *Dhatu's* in number. They arise from each other when cooked by effulgence of *Pitta*.^[64]

Karma of Dhatu's^[65]

- *Rasa's karma* is to satisfy contentment and nourish all other *Dhatu's*.
- *Karma* of blood – life; to keep the animal alive.
- The function of the *Mansa* is to cover or cover the ends, nerves and bones.
- *Meda's karma* is to keep the whole body aliphatic.

Swaroopa Ras Dhatu

The essential part of a well digested food is called '*Rasa*' and is thin in consistency, white, cold, and sweet, aliphatic and always movable.

Swaroopa of Rakta Dhatu

When the *Rasa* reaches the liver and spleen, the *Raga* (redness), and *Pak* by the pigmented bile there becomes blood.

Importance of Rakta Dhatu

The *Rakta Dhatu* permeates the whole body and is the best support for the soul. It's a *Sneha-yukta, Guru*, and sweet in nature. But when gets vitiated gets sour in taste like *Pitta dosha*.^[67]

Kala for the Dhatu Poshana

3015 *Kala* is the required for the *ahara-ras* to turn into the next *Dhatu* and in 18090 *Kala* time span is required for the nourishment of all the *Dhatu's*. Within one month all the *Dhatu* gets nourished.^[68]

Time taken for Dhatu Parinamana.

Sr.No	Dhatu	Charak	Sushruta
1	Rasa	1 day	1 day
2	Rakta	2 day	5 day
3	Mansa	3 day	10 day
4	Meda	4 day	15 day
5	Asthi	5 day	20 day
6	Majja	6 day	25 day
7	Shukra	7 day	3 day

Dhatu & Updhatu^[69]

Dhatu	Updhatu
Rasa Dhatu	Stanya & Artava
Rakta Dhatu	Sira & Kandara
Mansa Dhatu	Vasa & Twaka
Meda Dhatu	Snayu & Sandhi

Dhatu & Dhatu Mala^[70]

Dhatu	Dhatu Mala
Rasa	Kapha
Rakta	Pitta
Mansa	Karna Mala, Netra Mala, Asya Mala, Nasa Mala, RomaKupa Mala
Meda	Sweda
Asthi	Roma & Nakha
Majja	Charma Sneha, Netra Vita & Pureesha Sneha
Shukra	-----

Drug Review**Haritaki**

It originates in the homeland of the God *Hara* (i, e, Himalaya), and greenish in appearance, and useful in all types of diseases, it is called as *Haritaki*.

Latin Name: Terminalia chebula

Family: -Combretacea

Rasa: - *Haritaki* is *Kasaya* (astringent), *Amla*, *Tikata*, *Katu*, and *Madhur* in taste. Except salty Taste all the rest five taste are present in *Haritaki*.

Part of *Haritaki* has different taste

- *Twaka*- *Katu Ras*,
- *Meda*- *Kashaya Ras*,
- *Medoantantare*- *Amla ras*,
- *Asthisanshritam* - *Amla &*

- *Antare (madhyambhag) - Tikkata.*

Guna- *Ruksha, Ushana, Laghu, Bruhaniya, Pancharasatmak Kashaya Pradhan, Ushana Viraya, Madhur Paka.*

Anulomaka, Deepana, Pachaka, Ayushyama, Paushatika, Vayasthapani Sarva-roga Prashamani –Its useful in almost all the diseases explained in Ayurveda due to its *Guna, Viraya* and effect on body.

Action

Sour taste it pacifies *Vata Dosha*, Sweet & Bitter taste it pacifies *Pitta Dosha, Ruksha Guna* & *Kashaya Rasa* it pacificies *Kapha Dosha*. Hence it pacifies all the three *Dosha*'s.

Chemical content:-Chebulinic acid, chebulagic acid, corilagin, 18 amino acid.

Sr, no	Variety	Textual Character	Presumed Character	Uses
1	<i>Vijaya</i>	Having Alabu shape	Elongated shape without ridges and <8gm	Used in all diseases
2	<i>Rohini</i>	Round in shape	Circular, without ridges yellow colour	Used in Vrana
3	<i>Pootna</i>	Size is small with stony mesocarp and bid seed	Very small size with <4gm weight, with stony mesocarp and bid seed	External purpose
4	<i>Amirtha</i>	Mesocarp is more and fleshy	Mesocarp is more and fleshy with small seed < 7gm	Used for shodhana Karma
5	<i>Abhya</i>	Fruits having 5 ridges	Fruits having 5 ridges and weight 7-9 gm	Used for eye diseases
6	<i>Jivanthi</i>	Fruit is golden yellow	Fruit is golden yellow	Used for all diseases
7	<i>Chetaki</i>	Fruits having 3 ridges	Fruits having 3 ridges and weighs 5-7 gm	Used as purgatives

Contraindication

- Thirst, Dryness of mouth, Lockjaw, Dysphagia, early stage of fever, Emaciation, Pregnant women.
- *Ajirana, Ruksha Gunatmaka Ahara* intake on daily basis, *Stri-Madya-Visha Sevan* resulted in *Karshita*.

Useful part—*Shashyani* (seedless fruit).

Consumption of *Haritaki* in the seasons as bellows gives properties of *Rasayana* and cures all diseases.^[84]

- 1) *Grishama Ritu- Jaggery,*
- 2) *Varsha Ritu- Saidhavha lavana,*
- 3) *Sharda Ritu- Sharkara,*
- 4) *Hemant Ritu- Suntha Churna,*
- 5) *Shishir Ritu- Pipali churna,*
- 6) *Vasant Ritu-Honey,*

Rasayana Use of Haritaki^[85]

- 1) 2-2 *Haritaki* if taken with *Jaggery, Honey, Sunthi, Pipali, or Krushana Lavana as Anupana* for 1 year that person will be healthy for 100 years of life.
- 2) 1 *Haritaki* cooked in *Ghhrita* and have the remaining *Ghhrita*, it provides *Bala* to a person for longer duration.

***Bibhitaki*^[86]**

Latin Name:-Terminalia Bellirica

Family: - Combratacae

Guna: *Ushana Viraya Heema Sparsh Bhedanam Ruksha*

Vipaka: *Madhur*

Veerya: *Ushna*

Doshaghna: *Tridoshaghna*

Chemical composition

It contains triterpen oils including bellericid, b - sitosterol, saponin, glycosides bellericain polyphenols, lignans and fixed yellow oil.

Karma

It is mainly *Kaphashamak* - because of its *Ruksha, Laghu Guna* and *Kashaya Rasa*.

***AMALAK*^[87]**

Latin Name: *Embilica officinalis*

Family: Euphorbiaceae

Gana: - *Vayasthapana, Virechana-opaga*

Triphala, Purushakadi

Rasa: - *Kasaya, Madhur, Amla, Katu, & Tikkata* in taste.

Amla Rasa pacifies *Vata Dosha*,

Madhur Rasa + Shitaguna pacifies Pitta Dosha

Ruksha + Kashaya Rasa pacifies Kapha Dosha.

Guna: - *Vrusya*, used in fever, *Rasayana*

Kevala-Amalaka Rasayana: - In it only pure *Amalaki* is taken as single drug leading to person as *Yathartha – Vakata*.^[89] *Pittaghna* - by *Kashaya* and *Madhur Vipak* and *Vatashamak* by *Ushna Veerya*.

Rasayana of Amalaki^[93]

1) After having healthy diet person if takes *Aamalaki Rasa* with honey, sugar or *Ghrita* daily, all the diseases of old age stay away from the person.

Ghrita

New ghee:-New ghee is *Tarpak*, *Shramhar*, *Balashaya*, *Pandu-Roga*, and *Kamala-Roga*, as well as it's effective in eye disorder.

Purana Ghee:-Ten year kept old ghee is called as *Purana Ghrita*. It's a best ghee and cures *Timir Vyadhi*. It's *Kustha*, *Apasmara*, *Unmada*, and *Graha-Dosha Nashaka*. More than 10 year old ghee is *Rasayana*.

Kumbha Sarpish:- Ghee kept for 100 years are called as *Kumbha Sarpisha*, it is used in *Rashasa Graha Badha*.

Mahaghrita:- Ghee kept for more than 100 years are called as *Mahaghrita*, as it becomes old its properties get enhanced.

Ghrita Murchana^[100]

Ghee – 1 prastha, *Pathya – 1 pala*, *Dhatri – 1 pala*, *Vibhitaki – 1 pala*, *Jaladhara – 1 pala*, *Rajani – 1 pala*

Matulunga Drava – 1 pala, *Jal – 1 prastha*

Procedure

- 1) Ghee is taken in a clean wide mouthed iron vessel. Heated gently for 3 – 5 minutes, taken out of fire.
- 2) Take fine powder of herbal ingredients mentioned above mix with citron and make paste.
- 3) Add above paste to the ghee.
- 4) Water added.

- 5) Start heating this mix till only the ghee part remains. Filter. The final product obtained – is called *Murchita Ghrita*.
- 6) At the end stage of heating, the regular signs of herbal ghee preparation (*Ghruta Paka Lakshana*) should be observed. These signs are –good aroma, good colour.
- 7) Initially there will be frothing. At the end stage, frothing subsides.
- 8) Lack of sound when the ghee or the paste is put on fire.

As per Bhaishajya Kalpana, ghee is said to have ama dosha, especially if it is exposed to moisture. This means, ghee can cause indigestion on higher Doses. If *Ghrita Murchan* is done, then this Ama dosha will be removed from the ghee. This ghee is used as base on for all herbal oil preparation.

Methodology

1. Type of Study Design: - Before and after clinical study design.
2. LOCATION OF STUDY: - Research institute, hospital and periphery.
3. DURATION OF STUDY: - Study was be carried out for 18 month after approval of synopsis.

CENTRE OF STUDY: - Our college and periphery of college.

4. Sampling Technique: Purposive Sampling.
 5. Statistical Tests
 - Paired t test, for Objective Parameters.
 - Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Subjective Parameters.
 6. Method Of Selection of Study subject
- Inclusive Criteria
- Having signs and symptoms of *Pandu-Roga* (IDA). [Hb-8mg/dl to 10mg/dl].
 - Age group in between 20 to 50 yr.
 - Subject who gives consent for the procedure.

Exclusive Criteria

- Volunteers having secondary anemia.
- Volunteers having age below 20yr and above 50yr.
- Volunteers who keeps poor follow up.
- Volunteers having any allergic history.
- Pregnant and lactating women.

- Patient with Congenital Anemia .e.g., Thalassemia, Sickle cell Disease, Aplastic Anemia.
- Volunteers suffering from grievous disease like T. B, Aids, Cancer, etc.

DROP OUT

- Those patient who kept poor follow up or
 - The patient in which adverse effect occurs or
- If patient need any emergency medicine for relief such patient will be drop out from the study. So such patient will not be considered in this study.

7. Method of Data Collection Relevant to Objective:

A] By history taking

B] By assessment criteria

Already diagnosed patient of Pandu Subjects having Hb% between 8 to 10 gm/dl.

8. Population definition and selection of sample

- All the patient of Pandu attending OPD, IPD and casualty of Research Institute will be considered in this study.
- Patient will be included in study by inclusion and exclusion criteria.

9. Sample Size

To calculate sample size previous work done “A clinical Study On *Pandu Roga* with special reference to Iron Deficiency Anemia with *Dhatravaleha*”. In the above study the finding were as below

Hb% before treatment – 9.95

Hb% after treatment - 11.25

Standard Deviation – 1.47

Hb% improved after treatment in respect to before treatment is 21.6% where ‘p’ value is <0.001 [Highly significant]

For Qualitative study formula will be

$4S.D/E^2$

Sample size = $4 \times S.D/ E^2$

= $4 \times 1.47 / [0.5 \times 0.5]$

= $4 \times 1.47 / 0.25$

= 4×5.88

= 23.52

Hence the sample size for the performing study will be 23.52 but due to some drop out and irregular follower will be excluded. So, total number of patients will be 30.

SELECTION OF DRUG

- Both drug *Triphala* and *Ghrita* is indicated independently as treatment of *Pandu Roga* in *Bruhatrayee* as well as *Laghutrayee*.
- ‘*Triphala Bhavit Shilajatu* in obesity’ work is done in college.
- *Triphala* with *Murchita Ghrita* is *Sarvarogaghani* in *Sushruta Samhita* and such Combination or formula is not studied in *Pandu Roga*.

Study design

Statistical analysis of data collect

Conclusion

Subjective Criteria

Objective Criteria

Before Treatment	After treatment
Hb%, RBC Count, MCV, MCH, MCHC, HCT,	Hb%, RBC Count, MCV, MCH, MCHC, HCT,

Therapy

Route of administration	5gm <i>Triphala Churna</i> with 15gm <i>Murchhita Ghrita</i> [<i>Shudhitta Awastha</i> twice a day]
Duration of clinical study on single volunteer	45 day
Follow up	15thday, 30th day, 45th day.

OBSERVATION

Lakshana	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Alparaktata	<i>Panduta</i> Present at <i>Netra</i>	<i>Panduta</i> Present at <i>Netra, Nakha, Jivha</i>	<i>Panduta</i> Present at <i>Netra, Nakha, Jivha, Hastatala, Twacha</i>
Agnimandya	Digestion in 5hrs	Digestion in 7 hrs	Digestion in 9hrs
Daurbalya	After routine work	During routine work	Cannot perform routine work
<i>Aarohana Ayasen Shwas</i>	Stepping upto > 20 steps	Between 10-12 steps	< 10 steps
Hridaya Spansdana	Palpitaion after moderate exersion	Palpitation on mild exersion	Palpitation even at rest
Alpavak	Talks	Talks very less	Does not talk
Jwar prachiti	Absent	Absent or present	Absent or present
Akshikuta shota	Absent	Present	

Title of study "EVALUATION OF EFFICACY OF *TRIPHALA CHURNA* WITH *MURCHHITA GHRITA* IN *PANDU ROGA*– A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON *SAMANYA VISHESH SIDDHANT*".

Patients were selected according to the inclusive criteria, who were willing for the study consent were taken. For the present clinical study 30 patients ranging from age 20-50 were taken. The outcomes were measured before and after the completion of the treatment by both the objectives as well as subjective criteria. Data analysis consisted of two parts,

- To describe the characteristics of the subjects by using descriptive methods with help of general points like age, sex, diet, *Prakruti*, *Vyasan*, etc.
 - Comparison of pre-treatment measurements of the outcomes with that of post-treatment.
- All the observed data is presented below after the final statistical analysis as it is.

Age Distribution

Age in years	No. of individuals	Percentage
20 – 25	9	30
26 – 30	10	33.33
31 – 35	3	10
36 – 40	3	10
41 - 45	5	16.67
Total	30	100
Mean age ± SD (Range)	30.46 ± 7.71 (20 – 45)	

Gender distribution of study population

Gender	No. of individuals	Percentage
Male	5	16.67
Female	25	83.33

Distribution of study population according to marital status

Marital status	No. of individuals	Percentage
Unmarried	18	60
married	12	40

Distribution of *Ahar* on the basis of veg & Non-veg diet.

Type of diet	Veg		
	Mixed	8	26.67

Comparison of objective parameters before and after therapy.

Parameter	BT		AT		t-value	p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Hb%	9.19	0.71	9.27	0.73	2.7801	0.0094,HS
RBC	4.38	0.37	4.41	0.38	1.7328	0.0938,NS
HCT	28.57	5.17	28.70	5.18	4.4253	0.0001, HS
MCV	74.77	15.68	74.85	15.61	2.5878	0.0149,S
MCH	24.32	5.08	24.93	5.12	3.3392	0.0023,HS
MCHC	29.94	3.93	29.11	6.20	0.8589	0.3974,NS

From above shows that comparison of objective parameters before and after treatment.

- There was significant increase in hemoglobin after treatment with p-value of 0.0094, highly significant.
- Mean RBC before treatment was 4.38 ± 0.37 and after treatment it was 4.41 ± 0.38 . There was no significant change in RBC values after treatment with p-value of 0.0938 not significant.
- Mean hemoglobin before treatment was 9.19 ± 0.71 and after treatment it was 9.27 ± 0.23 . Mean HCT values before treatment was 28.57 ± 5.17 and after treatment it was 28.70 ± 5.18 . There was significant increase in HCT values after treatment with p-value of 0.0001, highly significant.
- Mean MCV values before treatment was 74.77 ± 15.68 and after treatment it was 74.85 ± 15.61 . There was significant increase in MCV values after treatment with p-value of 0.0149, significant.
- Mean MCH values before treatment was 24.32 ± 5.08 and after treatment it was 24.93 ± 5.12 . There was significant increase in MCH values after treatment with p-value of 0.0023, highly significant.
- Mean MCHC values before treatment was 29.94 ± 3.93 and after treatment it was 29.11 ± 6.20 . There no significant change in MCHC values after treatment with p-value of 0.3974, not significant.

Comparison of subjective criteria before and after treatment

Factor	Scale	BT	AT	Z-value	p-value
<i>Alparaktata</i>	Normal	0	10	4.359	<0.001,HS
	Mild	21	20		

	Moderate	9	0		
<i>Agnimandya</i>	<i>Manda</i>	14	14	--	--
	<i>Vishama</i>	12	12		
	<i>Tikshana</i>	4	4		
<i>Daurbala</i>	Normal	3	21	5.196	<0.001,HS
	Mild	18	9		
	Moderate	9	0		
<i>Arohen Ayasen Shwas</i>	Normal	16	29	3.207	0.0013,HS
	Mild	14	1		
<i>Hriday spandan</i>	Normal	18	30	3.464	0.0005,HS
	Mild	12	0		
<i>Alpavak</i>	Normal	20	30	3.162	0.0016,HS
	Mild	10	0		
<i>Jwara Prachiti</i>	Normal	30	30	--	--
	Mild	0	0		
	Moderate	0	0		
<i>Akshikuta shoota</i>	Normal	30	30	--	--
	Mild	0	0		

Above table showed severity of different symptoms before and after treatment.

- In *Alparakta* symptoms, 21 (70%) patients were mild severity and 9(30%) patients had moderate severity before treatment. After treatment, 10(33.33%) patients were in normal and 20(66.67%) patients had mild severity. There was significant decrease in severity of *Alparakta* after treatment. Hence treatment was effective in reduction in severity of *Alparakta*.
- In *Agnimadya* symptom, there was no change in severity of *Agnimandya* after treatment. There was no effect of treatment on severity of *Agnimandya*.
- In *Daurbalya* symptoms, 3(10%) were in normal category, 18(60%) patients had mild severity and 9(30%) patients had moderate severity of *Daurbalya* before treatment. After treatment, 21(70%) patient were in normal category and 9(30%) patients in mild severity. There was significant decrease in severity of *Daurbalya* after treatment with P value of <0.001, highly significant. Hence treatment had effect on reduction of severity of *Daurbalya*.
- In *Arohen Ayasen Shwas* symptom, 16(53.33%) patients were in normal category and 14(46.67%) patients were in mild severity category before treatment. After treatment, 29(96.67%) were in normal category and only 1(3.33%) patient was in mild category. There was significant reduction in severity of *Arohen Ayasen Shwas* symptoms after

treatment. Hence treatment given had significant effect on reduction in severity of *Arohen Ayasen Shwas* symptoms.

- In *Hriday spandan* symptoms, 18(60%) patients were in normal category and 12(40%) patients had mild severity symptoms before treatment. After treatment, all 30(100%) patients were normal. Hence there was significant effect of treatment on symptoms of *Hriday Spandan* symptoms.
- In *Alpavak* symptoms, 20(66.67 %) patients were in normal category and 10(33.33%) patients had mild severity symptoms before treatment. After treatment, all 30(100%) patients were normal. Hence there was significant effect of treatment on symptoms of *Alpavak* symptoms
- In *Jwara Prachiti and Akshikuta shoota* symptom, All 30(100%) patients were normal.

DISCUSSION

Ayurveda is one of the major health care system developed since human civilization in the Indian subcontinent which is based upon the experiences with nature and natural resources. Scientific evidences to prove the rationale of using this formulation in health care are essential to develop and prevent cultural heritage Ayurveda is based on empirical knowledge of Indian medical professionals for a long time. However, there is a long gap regarding all information due to lack of documentation.

On Conceptual Data

Pandu roga is result due to *Rasavaha-strotodushti janya vyadhi* according to charak and *Rasvahastrotas DushtiVyadhi janya vyadhi*. Indirectly it shows it's a *strotoavarodha janya vyadhi* means *Santarpanjanya Vyadhi* results in malnourished formation of *Sapta dhatus*.

Guna

<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Avastha</i>	<i>Guna</i>
<i>Kapha</i>	<i>Shina</i>	<i>Snigdha, Shita, Guru, Manda, Sthira</i>
<i>Pitta</i>	<i>Vridhdha</i>	<i>Tikashana, Ushana, Laghu, Sar</i>
<i>Vatta</i>	<i>Prakopa</i>	<i>Shita</i>
<i>Dushaya</i>	<i>Avastha</i>	<i>Guna</i>
<i>Rakta</i>	<i>Shina</i>	<i>Sar, Ushna</i>
<i>Mansa</i>	<i>Shina</i>	<i>Snigdha Guna Shina</i>
<i>Meda</i>	<i>Shina</i>	<i>Snigdha Guna Shina</i>
<i>Mala</i>	<i>Shina</i>	----
<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Shina</i>	<i>Drava Guna Shina</i>
<i>Sweda</i>	<i>Shina</i>	<i>Ushana, Drava, Guna, Shina</i>

Vrudhi Samanaihi Sarvesham

<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Bhibhitaki</i>	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Ghrita</i>
<i>Tikshna</i>	-	-	--	<i>Sanskarasya-anuvartanat</i>
<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	-	<i>Sanskarasya-anuvartanat</i>
<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	-	-	-
<i>Sar</i>	-	-	<i>Sar</i>	<i>Sanskarasya-anuvartanat</i>

Viparita Guna Chikitsa

<i>Pandu Roga</i>	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Bibhitaki</i>	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Ghrita</i>
<i>Snigdha</i>	<i>Ruksha</i>	<i>Ruksha</i>		
<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>		
<i>Guru</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Laghu</i>		
<i>Manda</i>				<i>Sanskarasya anuvartanat</i>
<i>Sthira</i>			<i>Sar</i>	<i>Sanskarasya anuvartanat</i>

Pandu Roga Guna Discussion

Pandu Roga is a *Doshaja* as well as *Agantuja Vyadhi* stated different types by different Acharyas as discussed in review. Definitely, *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* gets developed due to the vitiation of *Doshaja*, can be identified by the *Guna* of the symptoms present in the *Purava-Roop* and *Roopa* of the diseases and the *Chikitsa Siddhanta* say that treatment must be done by *Dravya, Guna* or *Karma* of *Ahara, Vihara* and *Aushadhi*.

In *Pandu-Roga* the pitta *Pradhana Tridosha* vitiation is seen, whereas the symptoms are observed in mixed form as stated by *Ashtang Sangraha* as

Kapha Shinata is observed so same way there is *Kshinta* of *Snigdhatata, Shitata, Guruta, Mandata*, and *Sar Guna*.

Pitta Vriddhi is seen which shows *Tikshana, Ushna, Sar Guna* whereas, *Vatta Prakopa* is observed so aggravation of *Shita Guna* is seen.

“*Roga Sarvoapi mandagnao*”

According to the *Samprapti* firstly *Agnimandya* is seen and it results in *Apakwa Ahara Ras* along with *Ama-Uttapatti*. As an initial stage of treatment as *Agnimandya* was present *Deepan-Pachanatamak Sunthi* with *Koushana jal* was given on empty stomach so, that *Amata* gets down.

Here, the *Guna* of the *Haritaki & Amalaki* are same except the *Virya*. Both acts in a similar manner as *Deepan, Pachaka* that means it helps in *Agni Deepan* and *Pachana* of the *Ama* present in the *Amashaya*. *Anulomakar* is also the *karma* of *Haritaki* through which constipation gets abolished and *Karya* of *Apana Vayu* becomes normal which again helps in *Agni-Deepan*.

As *Agni-mandya* is corrected, all the *Dhatva Agni's* get *Bala* from *Jatharagi*, the *Anana-Abhilasha Laksha* gets demolished. *Shaya* in the *Dhatu* gets corrected due to the correction in the respective *Dhatva-Agni* at the minute level. So the *Shaya* or abnormal formation of the *Dhatu* like *Rakta, Mansa* and *Meda Dhatu* gets to the normal level.

As *Ghrita* shows *Swar-varnaprasadana* karma and the normalization of the pitta *Dosha* gives the Normal colour to the skin.

As the formation of the *Meda Dhatu* gets normal so the *swedapravrutti* which was diminish due to the *Dhatushaya* gets level up.

Dhatu shaithilya and *indriyashaithilya* formed in the disease gets corrected due to the *Deepan –Pachaka Gunas* of *Haritaki, Amalaki, Bihitaki* and *Ghhrit*. But the *Snigdha Guna* of the *Ghrita* don't aggravates the *Dhatu Shaithilya* as its *Murchita Ghrita*, As *Agnimandya* get corrected, all the *Dosha's* get level up and the *Angamarda, Shita Dweshi*, etc symptoms to get dissolved slowly.

As discussed above the *Guna's* of *Pandu Roga's*, *Guna* of the drugs are. For the treatment according to the *Samanya Vishesh Siddhanta* both *Samnya & Viparyaya Chikitsa* are important but in *Pandu Roga Viparayaya Chikitsa* is seen more beneficial in milder anaemia.

Ras Shaya Lakshanas Corelated to Pandu Roga

Acharya Charak Stated *Pandu Roga* is *Rasavahastrotas Dusthti-Janya Vyadhi*. *Dushita Rasja Roga* shows the same as *Ashradha, Aruchi, Asyavairasya Arasnyata, Gaurava, Tandra Angamarda*, are the same as the symptoms of the *Pandu Roga* if correlated. Both are created in the body due to *Agnimandya* by vitiated *Dosha*, leading to the formation of *Ama Yukta Ras Dhatu*.

Pandu-Roga and Anaemia

Anaemia is a condition in which the oxygen and carbondioxide carrying capacity of the blood gets low due to decreased in Hb% than the normal value. So, the symptoms of the anemia are the same as of *Pandu Roga* i.e., fatigue, palpitation, weakness, and tachycardia, etc. Study was done on correlation of *Pandu Roga* type with the type of anemia which suggest that Ayurvedic *Pandu-Roga* and Anaemia can be correlated.

Triphala is gentle laxative. So, it protect the patients from constipation effects caused due to *Mandagni*. It obvious from constituent described above that all the *Agni* and *Dhatvagni* upto normal level and *Dhatunirman* process gets tone up which results ultimately to *Dhatu Pushti* and *Dhatu Prasadana*.

Doshaghanata:-All the drug used to treat *Pandu roga* in study has *Tridosahar* Property. So it becomes helpful in treating *Tri-Doshaja Pandu Roga*.

Guna

Tikshana Guna of most of the drugs have *Ama Pachan* and *Stroso- Sudhikar* property. *Mandagni* is the motive cause for *Pandu Roga* and *Triphala Churna* and *Ghhrita* having *Deepan & Pachana* property. So, diminishes *Mandagni* and breaks the pathogenesis of *Pandu Roga*. It also promotes the *Dhatvaagni* and as a results *Dhatupushti* process is motivated.

Effect on strotas

Maximum number of *Dravya* possesses *Laghu, Ruskha-Guna, Tikta & Kashaya Rasa*. So, it possess the *Stroto – Shudhikar* property that's why it's able clarify the *Strotas*.

Rasa

Majority of drug in *Triphala* has *Tikta -Amla –Katu Rasa* causing the action of *Deepan, Pachana*. So, the drug increases *Jatharagani* and *Dhatava-Agni* up to the normal level results in *Dhatupushti* and *Dhatu Prasadana*.

Demographic Data**1] Age**

Cases for the study were selected of the age in between 20-50 year. *Pandu* which is co-related with *IDA* commonly affects the age group 26—30year. The age group can be distinguished as *Madhyama* and *Vrudha Vaya Avastha* and mainly *Madhyama Avastha* gets affected. In this age group there is *Pitta Dosha* dominance and vitiated *Dosha* results in *Animandhya* that is the most important *Hetu* of *Pandu Roga*.

2) Gender

As for gender is concerned in present study, it is observed that 83.33% were female and 16.67% were male individual. Generally female gets indulge in *Adhyasana, Vishamasana* etc, due to household work, lack of exercise, improper diet or *Alpa Aharana Shakti*, etc. leads to *Angi-Dushati*, results in *Aam* formation hence *Dosha* vitiation is seen.

3) Education and Soio-economic status

Definitely as per the cases included in study according to the inclusion criteria had mediocore lifestyle so no much comments would be made.

4) Occupation

On interrogation about occupation status it was found majority of them were students 16 (53.33%) in number it may be due to students hectic routine, improper diet, lack of exercise,

lack of nutrition (Mess/Tiffin), housewives were 5 in number and labourer were also 5 in number. As the *Hetu*'s are same for as *Adhyasana*, *Diwaswaopa*, etc. leads to *Agni Dushti*.

5) *Vyasana*

Tea: - The present study shows of 30 cases 23 (76.67%) individual had habit of tea, which results in diminished *Abhyavarana Shakti* hence results in *Agni Dushti* and *Aam Uttapati*.

Betal nut: - *Oaj –Nashak*, *Vaisakhi*, *Dhatushaithilya* are the properties of betel nut, after regular use causes *Bhrama* in individual. Total number of 5(16.67%) cases are seen of betel nut consuming cases.

Tobacco: - Intake affects the heart, disturbs blood pressure, increase the ADH level which decrease the urine production, etc. It's has a *Kapha-Vattahar* and *Pittkar* properties results in imbalance of *Agni* constituent hence *Agni Dushti* is seen.

Alcohol: - 2(6.67%) individuals had *Vyasana* of alcohol intake.

6) Diet:- 22(73.33%) cases were taking mixed diet while rest individuals i.e., 8 were taking vegetarian diet. Non-veg is heavy to digest i.e., *guru Ahara* must be considered on account of already existing *Mandagni*.

7) *Prakruti*: 18 (60%) cases were of *Vata-Kapha Prakruti* followed by 7 (23.33%) cases were of *Vata-Pitta Prakruti* according to the data collected on examination concludes that *Pandu Roga* is the result of *Partantra Hetu Dushti Vyadhi* as per the *Prakruti Pradhanata*.

8) *Ahara*:- *Agni* required for the digestion of *Ahara* can be measured by *Anumana Pramana* with the help of two steps

a) *Abhyavarana Shakti* that is capacity of amount of food intake

b) *Jarana Shakti* that is time required for the getting the *Jirna Lakshanas* after having the food.

c) 18(60%) cases had *Madhyama Ahyavarana Shakti* and 12(40%) cases had *Avara-Abhyavarana Shakti*.

9) *Vyayama*:- Out of 30 cases, 18 (60%) cases performed no exercise hence 12(40%) had *Avara Vyayama Shakti*, because of lack of exercise *Jathar-Agni Bala* gets diminished, leads to *Ama* production and results in various kind of disease.

CONCLUSION

Study was aimed to “Evaluation of Efficacy of *Triphala Churna with Murchhita Ghrita* in Pandu Roga– A Conceptual Study on *Samanya Vishesh Siddhant*”

The following conclusion are drawn after considering the clinical aspects and theoretical facts.

- 1) *Pandu-Roga* is majorly found in female of *Madhyama Avastha* than male.
- 2) The study disclosed the avenue properly for evaluating the therapeutic efficacy of a common preparation like '*Triphala*' on constipated bowel habit and wellbeing.
- 3) *Triphala Churna* with *murchita Ghrita* is *Tridoshghana dravya*.
- 4) *Haritaki* is *anulomankar* and *bhedaka* in property, *Ghrita anulomankar*.
- 5) *Triphala* with *Murchita* is effective in destruction of *Samprapti* of *Pandu Roga* with cyclic process of *Angimadhya* and *Aam Utapatti*.
- 6) *Pandu Roga's Guru, Manda, Sthira, Snigdha [Aam], Sheeta Guna's* gets to normal level due to *Ruksha, Ushana, Laghu Guna's* of *Haritaki Bibhitaki* and *Amalaki*.
- 7) It can be concluded that *IDA* is a *Nutrition Deficiency Anemia*.
- 8) *Folic acid and Vitamin B12* is required for maturation of *RBCs*.

Scope & Limitation of study

- 1) Study has been restricted to *Pandu-Roga* of mild *Anaemia* only.
- 2) More study can be done with large sample size and other type of *Anaemia* too.
- 3) Study with the same drug can be done with numbers of disease as its said *Sarva-Rogaghana* drug.
- 4) Single drug can be studied in same disease or different *Vyadhi*.

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